

Structural, Optical, Thermal and SEM studies of Pure and Ferric doped Potassium Penta Borate (KB5) Single Crystals

K.Prabha^{1*}, M. Shiniya Bommi² and M. Ramesh Babu³

^{1,2} Department of Physics, Mother Teresa Women's University, Kodaikanal, Tamilnadu, India

³Department of Physics, APA College of Arts & Culture, Palani

Abstract

The development of lasers has played a key role in the past five decades for the development of mankind in various fields and to reach several technological advancements. The demand for laser beams in the ultraviolet and visible regions is growing enormously. The laser beams in the UV and visible regions find applications in several industries, medical surgeries, data storage, optical communication, and entertainment purposes. Advances in semiconductor photolithography, for example, are creating demand for 158 and 193 nm coherent light sources, while emerging micromachining and material-processing applications also need deep-UV laser radiation. In addition, research scientists would like a widely tunable coherent light source down to 200 nm for laser spectroscopy and photochemical synthesis [1]. Potassium pentaborate (KB5) is a desirable inorganic nonlinear optical material which exhibits a low angular sensitivity and hence, proved useful for second harmonic generation (SHG) [2]. High damage threshold and wide transparency make it a better alternative for KDP crystals in frequency doubling and laser fusion experiments [3]. A single crystals of pure and Fe doped KB5 were harvested by slow-solvent evaporation techniques. The crystal structure is confirmed by Powder XRD. The optical absorbance studied by UV-Vis. The thermal behavior of pure and Fe doped KB5 discussed by TG-DTA spectrum. Surface studies are discussed by SEM studies.

References:

- [1] Arunkumar R, Journal of Chemistry, Volume 2013, Article ID 154862, 6 pages <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2013/154862> .
- [2] Voitsekhovskii V.N., Sov. Phys. Crystal, 27, pp. 322-323 (1982).

[3] Newman P.R., Warren L.F., Cunningham P., Chang T.Y., Copper D.E., Burdge G.L., Polak dingels P. and Lowe-Ma C.K., "Advanced Organic Solid State materials", Ed. 173, pp. 557-561 (1990).